

**D.4.3.4. Report on risk
assessment and modelling
of animal coronavirus
evolution**

JIP COVRIN WP4

Responsible Partners: BfR

Contributing partners:

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Leader	Racem Ben Romdhane (BfR – P9)		
Other contributors	Matthias Filter (BfR – P9)		
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REPORT ON RISK ASSESSMENT AND MODELLING OF ANIMAL CORONAVIRUS EVOLUTION

1. Introduction

COVRIN aims to integrate research by One Health EJP partner institutes on the topics of SARS-CoV-2 emergence, risk assessment and preparedness. The project has two main operational objectives: (i) to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2, and (ii) to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2. To achieve these objectives, integrative research activities are focused on four topics:

- (i) research on detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal species and the environment;
- (ii) research on SARS-CoV-2 molecular and biological characterization;
- (iii) SARS-CoV-2 surveillance and risk assessment, focussed on the animal human interface; and
- (iv) coronavirus preparedness.

The overall aim of the COVRIN project is to generate and share data of these integrative research activities, in order to increase the preparedness for future coronavirus outbreaks.

The WP 4 aims to investigate the coronavirus preparedness through the study of virus – host interactions, potential of virus evolution and host adaptation.

2. Description of the task

The objective in subtask 4.3.4 is to investigate the application potential of data and research outcomes generated within COVRIN for virus emergence and evolution risk assessments to finally help to improve surveillance and control strategies.

In this subtask, data from COVRIN WPs 1, 2, 3 and 4 were analysed on their potential to be integrated into future risk assessments, e.g. on the question which animal species/conditions offer the highest potential for future virus emergence. This work includes

- i) the definition of an One Health risk assessment framework that is capable of assessing risks originating from zoonotic hazards in an integrated One Health approach, and
- ii) an overview on how specific results from the COVRIN project and other publicly available resources could contribute to such an One Health SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment.